

Deliverable

Workpackage

Responsible Partner: Norwegian
Institute of Public Health

Contributing partners: Sciensano, SVA

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	D-JRP6-1.1 / Glossary of terms based on a common food borne zoonosis surveillance terminology
WP and Task	WP1 (JRP6-WP1-T1: Definition of a joint food borne zoonosis surveillance terminology)
Leader	Norwegian Institute of Public Health
Other contributors	Sciensano, SVA
Due month of the deliverable	M24
Actual submission month	M21
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.</i> <i>OTHER</i>	R
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU

GLOSSARY OF TERMS BASED ON A COMMON FOOD BORNE ZONOSIS SURVEILLANCE TERMINOLOGY

1. Results and collaborations

Given the work on a Med-Vet glossary of the participants of ORION project WP2 Integration in which members of NOVA project WP1 also participated in the first year, in order to complete the deliverable of this WP, a collaboration has been established with the respective ORION team, as well as COHESIVE.

WP1-T1 has collected 274 terms from partners leading all WPs. The NOVA Glossary has been delivered to ORION project leader, BfR, in the second half of June 2019 in order to incorporate the NOVA Glossary into the common OH Glossary. In the period between July and October 2019, there has been several exchanges with BfR in order to adjust the NOVA Glossary into the common version. The final result can be found here: <https://ckan-aginfra.d4science.org/organization/about/orionknowledgehub>

The OHEJP Glossary has 3 main functionalities. First the collection of One Health (OH) related terms and definitions in the sectors public health, animal health and food safety. Second, highlighting similarities and differences of terms and definitions between the sectors. Finally an infrastructure to reference, search and filter terms and definitions.

As an outcome of this cooperation (of all three projects) is a common article that is currently (December 2019) being drafted. This publication work is coordinated by BfR.